

D13.3: Infrastructure services testing report

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1. Document History

Version	Date	Contributors	Activity
0.1	July 29 th 2015	Bernard Pinglier	Draft structure of document
0.2	November 17 th 2015	Roberto Scopigno, Matteo Dellepiane	Review Proposed structure questionnaire Visual Media Service
0.3	December 11 th 2015	Federico Nurra Kai Salas Rossenbach Amala Marx Emmanuelle Bryas	Added Images Added References Modified Tables Added test prototype
0.3.1	December 18 th 2015	Holly Wright	Quality Control
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2. Introduction

This deliverable D13.3 presents the initial results of Task 13.4 (T13.4), which is part of Work Package 13 (WP13) in the ARIADNE Project.

As stated in the Description of Work (DoW) of the ARIADNE Project, the main objectives of WP13 are:

- *To analyse, select, design and deploy the service components of the integrated infrastructure in order to improve the provision of the online services to the researchers*
- *To take into account in the design and the deployment further enhancements of the service architecture as required by the additional implementation of results from WP14-WP17*

The tasks of the WP13 are:

Task 13.1 – Service Design and Specifications

Task 13.2 – Service Implementation

Task 13.3 – Long-term Preservation Services

Task 13.4 – Acceptance Testing

The Task will be in charge of testing the services produced in Task 13.2 and verify their correspondence to design (Task 13.1), use requirements (Task 12.1) and users' specifications (Task 2.1 and Task 2.2). New or improved services may be approved and passed to the next Task or returned to 13.2 for amendments. Testing will be carried out on a specific testing environment prepared by the partners in charge of the task. They will set up a number of simulated research contexts, relevant for archaeological research, and will compare the behaviour of the system with the expected one. They will furthermore verify overall compliance with requirements and the performance of the system in simulated real conditions. Such tests will be performed regularly. Their outcomes will be reported to the lead partner of Task 13.2 for the necessary feedback. The testing specifications and the routine testing mechanism will be detailed in Task 13.1.

As shown in the following figure, taken from document D13.1, task T13.4 is related to most work packages and tasks within the ARIADNE project:

Figure 1: ARIADNE Tasks and Service Design

This report focuses on the following aspects:

- Overview of design, use requirements and user's specifications, the compliance with which the services have to be tested (see D13.1, D12.1 and D2.2 for a more detailed presentation)
- Services to be evaluated: functional description and progress report for implementation of these (see D13.2 for a more detailed presentation)
- Methodology used for the tests
- First testing results. Informal tests have been conducted by Inrap among a community of internal power users, showing a great interest in the service provided for visualization of 3D images, but also the need for enhanced visualization and analysis tools, and especially measuring tools
- Most of the work remains to be done starting in January 2016, when a comprehensive set of services will gradually be made available, including the services related to the Catalogue

3. Related Work

3.1. User Requirements (D12.1)

This document is a deliverable (D12.1) of the ARIADNE project (“Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe”), which is funded under the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme. D12.1 is associated with Task 12.1 within WP12, which is titled ‘Implementing’ Interoperability, and falls within the larger ARIADNE conceptual framework for the ARIADNE e-Infrastructure.

The main objective of D12.1 is to understand the current landscape from which the ARIADNE infrastructure can be created, in order to inform the development of the ARIADNE portal and services. This landscape includes the data, metadata, ontologies and vocabularies available for use, along with any associated issues of licensing and access, informed by users’ needs.

3.2. Service Design (D13.1)

This document aims to specify the service design of the ARIADNE Portal, and provide a common vision, a user perspective on the functionality, and a framework to identify, discuss and validate the requirements for the underlying technical services. As such, the audience of this document was both technical and non-technical.

This service design was created using the following input: Description of Work, Task 2.1 (Survey of users’ needs and community building), Task 12.1 (Assessment of use requirements), an examination of existing portals and WP3-12-13 Workshop discussions. The service design provided input for Task 13.2 (Build Services) and Task 13.4 (Acceptance testing). The service design provided a common vision formulated in terms of principles, derived from the mission statement in the Description of Work.

3.3. Second report on users' needs (D2.2)

The main objective of this report was to provide additional, more detailed evidence about user requirements of key target groups (“users”) of the project with regard to the ARIADNE data portal. A panel of about 25 researchers was asked to describe in detail their use of digital data archives, to evaluate existing archives and other portals and to highlight useful features of these portals which could serve as “good practice” when creating a new research data portal. This information supports the ARIADNE project in taking informed decisions regarding the specification of the e-infrastructure and services so they are developed in a way that corresponds to perceived and actual research needs. The mandate was to provide evidence on these issues, notably through collecting feed-back from the ARIADNE community by way of a user survey.

3.4. Infrastructure Design (D12.2)

The main goal of Task 12.2 is to specify a resource integration and discovery mechanism for use in ARIADNE. The resources to be integrated are datasets and collections, GIS data, metadata schemas, ontologies and vocabularies available from the project partners, as well as institutions outside the ARIADNE consortium. This deliverable provides an overview of the ARIADNE architecture, including a summary of the conformance of the architecture to the data and standards requirements set out in D12.1, as well as to the specifications of the Services of the ARIADNE Infrastructure, presented in D13.1. This is followed by a content analysis of the main content types defined in D12.1, and the integration strategy for the two levels of content: the metadata integration, and the data integration. This will attempt to integrate selected resources (datasets and/or metadata) from particular partners/data providers and provide cross-search and access mechanisms to integrated resources, using a faceted search on “what”, “where”, “when” and “resource type”.

4. Overview of design, use requirements and users' specifications

The users' needs are summarized as follows, derived from D2.2:

1. **Overall focus** of the ARIADNE project is on data discovery and access services.
2. The primary focus of the design and interfaces of the data portal should be an **overview of what data is accessible**, including statistical information on quantity, types, and distribution (e.g. country/area, period).
3. The portal should focus on the **European/international dimension**. Lack of underlying resources (per country, type of data, etc.) should not be seen as a deficit, but used to promote data mobilization (e.g. implementation of national data archives).
4. Added value should also be created through **linking** data and publication **resources not held within the ARIADNE Registry** (e.g. metadata of document archives and open access publishers).
5. Linked Open Data (LOD) can play a core role for value generation, but **further uptake of LOD principles** by archaeological institutions and projects must be encouraged.
6. In the development of the data search, access and other services, **members of the user community must be thoroughly involved** and regular feedback on implemented solutions sought by the wider community.
7. **User-focused development of the portal services** and applications (relevance, usability, user-friendliness) should be at the top of the project's priorities.

8. **Services for websites for research communities** in particular subjects or geographic regions (e.g. alerts on relevant datasets) could greatly expand the reach of the data portal and, in turn, promote further data mobilization.

9. Full exploitation of the data resources (incl. metadata, conceptual knowledge) should be enabled by **interfaces for external applications** (e.g. a well-documented API, OAI-PMH target, SPARQL endpoint).

10. Support of e-research/science should, in the first instance, be provided through **integrating access to data resources** and by pointing users to existing tools for data extraction, processing and analysis.

The use requirements (D12.1) refer to the requirements for the design and specification of the subsequent tools and services necessary for integration. D12.1 produces recommendations for Datasets; Metadata Standards, Schemas and Vocabularies; and Access and Sharing Policies.

Datasets

- **Site and monument databases:** Most European countries and/or regions have them, and combining them may be useful for cross-border searching and geo-location
- **Intervention activity:** May have multiple activities associated with a geo-locatable site, which may allow linking of various activities to a single site or monument
- **Fieldwork databases:** Usually too diverse, so individual databases may not be useful for integration, but may be worth linking to intervention activities for bibliographic discovery
- Other **categories** are quite specific, but may be useful for integration:
 - **Scientific Databases**
 - **Artefact Databases**
 - **Burial Databases**

Balance data quality and quantity: specify requirements that datasets have to meet in order to be integrated, preferably using formal criteria.

The relationships between the types of data available from the content providing partners and the recommended integration activity to be designed within D12.2 are set out in the table below.

DATA Balance data quality and quantity	ARIADNE datasets					
	Sites and monuments databases	Intervention databases	Fieldwork databases	Artefacts	Burials	Scientific datasets
Integration activity						
Cross-border subject search	X	X	X			?
Cross-border period search	X	X	X			?
Map driven searching or visualisation	X	X	X		?	?
Bibliographic metadata from grey literature	X	X	X	X	X	X
Integration and interoperability from scientific databases						X
Integration of particular kinds of artefact data				X	X	
<i>Dataset assessment required</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+

Metadata Standards, Schemas and Vocabularies

- The **use of international standards for the documentation of excavations and monuments** so as to render it transparent and comparable and, above all, make them more interoperable.
 - **Free access to tools**, particularly for data mapping, to make it easier to incorporate these standards, and offering the means and guidance for archaeologists to deposit their digital records **in an appropriate archive**
 - **The sustainability of digital datasets** must also be high on the agenda
- The relationships between the wishes and concerns with regard to metadata and the recommended tools to be designated or designed within D12.2 are set out in the table below:

	Metadata schemas	Vocabularies	Metadata mapping tools	Metadata input tool	Metadata description tool	SKOSifier tool
Wishes						
Data transparency	+					
Data accessibility	++	+				
Metadata quality	+++	+++				
Data quality						
International dimension	++	+++				
Concerns						
Metadata quality (managers)					X	X
Effort for metadata creation (researchers)				X		
Anxiety about unfamiliar schemas (researchers)			X			

Table showing the wishes and concerns with regard to data standards, categorised by the type of schema or vocabulary which may address the wishes, and the tools which may address the concerns. The + signifies the level of importance.

Access and Sharing Policies

- **A common method of data citation should be established** for adoption by partners, and promoted by ARIADNE to the archaeological research community. Academic recognition is an important motivation for encouraging researchers to share access to their datasets
- **Allocation of DOIs or the equivalent to datasets ingested to the ARIADNE infrastructure** should be investigated. The system used should be capable of identifying sub-sets within collections. Persistent identification of datasets is important in underpinning data sharing and data citation
- **Content itself (databases, document archives, images, 3D models, etc.) should be provided to ARIADNE by content partners using the Creative Commons license suite** (version 4.0 is preferred) under license permissions agreed with the content owner. CC BY is recommended for open access. CC BY SA or CC BY SA NC licenses may also be applicable
- **A Collection description** (of the whole collection and subFsets within the collection) should be published under a CC BY license for each dataset ingested to the ARIADNE infrastructure
- **Metadata records should be published under a CCO license** – to enable integration of multiple datasets within the metadata repository, support resource discovery and enable linked open data

The Services Design (D13.1) introduces the functionality of the services, derived from a user perspective, and thus gives an important input for acceptance testing.

It presents a set of use cases representing various real situations encountered by members of the archaeological community:

- **Search and explore the Registry** to look for archaeological datasets to be previewed and/or downloaded:
The use case is divided in several steps (navigation, entering search parameters, displaying the results) and relates to several services e.g. portal access, timeline search, geographical search, display of the results, etc.
- **Preview data** to determine the relevance of this data for specific research:
The preview service and functionality depends on the nature of the data.
- **Access data** by downloading it for further processing
- **Deposit data** in the ARIADNE infrastructure to allow it to be browsed and re-used by fellow researchers:
The service requires a set of guidelines for depositing data and an archive compatible with the data to be deposited.
- **Search and access the service registry** to discover tools and knowledge to support research/data management activities
- **Prepare and register a new collection** in the Registry
- **Enrich Visual Media Documents** from one of the visual documents (3D models , RTI images, high resolution images, terrain models) stored in one of the catalogues associated with the ARIADNE Portal provide a visualization window showing the visual services that could be applied to visual media
- **Manage accounts** to allow a security manager to handle and control authentication and access. The security manager may have an overview of the users and eventually change their attributes

5. Services to be evaluated

This section gives an overview of the services to be evaluated, as they exist to date. More details can be found in document D13.2 (Initial Services Implementation Report).

5.1. ARIADNE Portal

The ARIADNE portal is the front-end facility by which the user will access the various services provided by ARIADNE infrastructure.

The development is led by DAI. It began in September 2015 and is planned to be completed by January 2016.

Figure 2: ARIADNE Portal – Home page

5.2. Services provided on the ARIADNE Catalogue

The ARIADNE Catalogue is based on the ACDM (Ariadne Catalogue Data Model), which describes the archaeological resources that are made available within the ARIADNE infrastructure to the researchers wishing to access and use them. The current version is ACDM 2.6, delivered on Sept. 26th, 2015.

5.2.1. Catalogue search

The search and retrieval functionalities for all kinds of resources described in the Catalogue are currently under development in the context of WP12 and should be delivered in January 2016.

The search and retrieval will be refined using several types of filters, including: type, resource type, subject, provider, period, publisher...

The filters reflect the structure of the ARIADNE Catalogue. They should guide the user not only in the phase of refining the search, but also in widening and completing the search.

<http://ariadne-portal.dcu.gr/>

The screenshot displays the ARIADNE Portal search interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Catalog', 'Services', 'Experiments', and 'About'. A search bar contains the text 'Start a new search...'. Below the navigation bar, the 'Current search' section shows a search bar with 'Search for resources...' and a refresh button. To the right, it indicates 'Total results: 30,130' and a pagination control showing page 1 of 3012.

On the left side, there are several filter sections:

- Where:** A map of Europe and the Mediterranean region.
- Resource type:** A list of categories with counts: 'Event/intervention resources' (29,974) and 'Sites and monuments databases or inventories' (156).
- Subject:** A text input field.
- Keyword:** A text input field.
- Contributor:** A text input field.
- Publisher:** A text input field.
- Place:** A text input field.

The main content area displays a list of search results, each with a calendar icon, a title, a type, a publisher, and a brief description:

- Longner Hall and short section of forecourt wall adjoining to NW LONGNER:** Type: Sites and monuments databases or inventories; Publisher: Archaeology Data Service. Description: Country house. 1803. by John Nash on site of earlier house. Red sandstone ashlar with grey sandstone ashlar dressings and details; red brick and rendered brick to rear of service wing; plain tile roof. 2-span over main range. Irregular L-plan; main block with 2 ranges with gabled cross-win...
- Round cairn on the summit of Heddon Hill:** Type: Sites and monuments databases or inventories; Publisher: Archaeology Data Service. Description: The trig point on Heddon Hill sits on top of a Bronze Age round cairn. The cairn survives in reasonable condition and measures 4m in diameter by 0.2m high. There is an outer kerb visible. The trig point has been built in the north east sector of the cairn and a greater portion remains undi...
- Moated Site in Moat Plantation (Newstreet Moat):** Type: Sites and monuments databases or inventories; Publisher: Archaeology Data Service. Description: Evaluated for MPP in 1990-1. Medium score as one of 133 Moated sites. Evaluated for MPP in 1990-1. Medium score as one of 91 Irregular Open Field Systems. Sited on very gently sloping land on the S side of a gentle EW ridge c200 m to the N. Well preserved rectangular moated site. The moat...
- Hut circle on Heddon Hill:** Type: Sites and monuments databases or inventories; Publisher: Archaeology Data Service. Description: Situated at NU 00572030 on a slight south-east facing slope is a circular platform formed by a crescentic back scarp on the uphill side making a level platform about 15m diameter partly bounded by and earth and stone bank 3m wide 0.5m high with an entrance on the south-east side. There are...
- Sheppards Pit (1):** Type: Sites and monuments databases or inventories; Publisher: Archaeology Data Service. Description: Three pits have been identified on Mangotsfield Road, all pre-dating 1750 (Southway 1972: 29). They worked the Cock, Chick and Hen seams in the Middle Pennant series. Only one of the pits is recognisable on the Mangotsfield Tithe map of 1843 (SGSMR 13110); it had a Newcomen engine by 17...
- Brook House:** Type: Sites and monuments databases or inventories; Publisher: Archaeology Data Service. Description: Farmhouse, latterly divided, now house. Mid-C17. Timber framed with plastered and painted brick infill, rubblestone and brick plinth; C20 machine tile roof. L-plan; 2 framed bays aligned approximately north-west/south-east with one bay gabled cross-wing projecting to north-east. Framing: s...

Figure 3: ARIADNE Portal – Textual research

BUILDING

Access resource on the web

Excavations at Mary Arches Street in 1975 (EUAD 54.00) recovered evidence of a number of phases of timber buildings which can be stratigraphically placed in the early period of the civil Roman administration of the area. At least four phases of rebuilding could be discerned. The earliest of these buildings had been destroyed by fire. Excavation conditions were far from ideal, and many of the observations were made in section only, so any further resolution of the stratigraphic sequence was not possible. Neither the overall form nor the function of these buildings could be determined from the available evidence. The buildings appeared to have been laid out on either side of a street laid down directly over the fortress buildings, and have thus been split into two monuments reflecting what were undoubtedly at least two separate structures.

TIMBER FRAMED BUILDING

Metadata

Identifier	11637864
Language	English
Resource type	Sites and monuments databases or inventories
Type	Dataset
Publisher	Archaeology Data Service [Organization]
Issued	2011-07-05 00:00:00.0
Contributor	Exeter City Council [Organization]

License Information

Access Rights	ADS Terms and Conditions
Access Policy	http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/advice/termsOfUseAndAccess

Resource is part of
<http://registry.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/collection/17017150>

Geographically similar

Thematically similar

- An archaeological watching brief at the Donkey Cart, Market Square, Petersfield, Hampshire
- BARRACK BLOCK
- TIMBER FRAMED BUILDING
- BIL 017 Archaeological Monitoring of rear of 128a High Street, Bildeston
- 10-12 The Wash, Hertford, Hertfordshire: Historic Building Appraisal.
- Outbuildings at Poyndon Farm, Silver Street, Goffs Oak, Hertfordshire: Historic Building Recording and Archaeological Monitoring and Recording
- North Rookery, Rowington

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Figure 4: ARIADNE Portal – Dataset view

5.2.2. Spatial search and display

The spatial search and display facility is currently under development by CNR-ISTI and DAI and should be delivered in January 2016.

This functionality takes advantage of the data provided in the ACDM, where indications about the geographical position of the elements of the collections are provided. This enables the user to visualize collections, which come from different providers, but are related to a common geographical area. The spatial search and display will be possible both by exploring the map and focusing on the area of interest, and by visualizing all the collections that come from a specific query on the map.

Figure 5: ARIADNE Portal – Geographical view of datasets

Figure 6: ARIADNE Portal – Detailed geographical view of datasets

5.2.3. Timeline search and display

The timeline search and display facility is currently under development by CNR-ISTI and DAI, and should be delivered in January 2016.

Similarly to spatial search and display, temporal search is possible due to the description of collections in the ARIADNE Catalogue Model. The work carried out within WP2 provided a set of period descriptions that refer to items in each collection.

The temporal search and display will provide a visual description of the items in the query, possibly displaying a timeline that will make it possible to zoom to selected sub-periods. The timeline will also be a possible starting point for other types of search.

5.3. Other Services created within the ARIADNE Project

5.3.1. Visual Media Services

A first version of the Visual Media Services was delivered by the Visual Computing Lab of CNR-ISTI in January 2015. This provides end users with the means to publish and visualize 3D datasets, RTI and high-resolution images on the web, with an easy and automatic procedure.

A second version is to be delivered in December 2015.

Currently, the Service gives the user the possibility for the user to upload a 3D model, an RTI Image or a high-resolution image. The Service will process the data by essentially completing two operations:

- Transform the item into a multi-resolution format, that could be used in a progressive rendering fashion for web visualization
- Create a simple visualization page, which will be stored and hosted by the Service. This simple page may also be downloaded by the user, in order to serve as a starting point for more complex visualization or integration in the context of other web pages.

The current version of the service is available at: <http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Figure 7: ARIADNE Visual Media Service – Home Page

Figure 8: ARIADNE Visual Media Service – 3D model view

5.3.2. Visual Media in archaeological collections

This service provides an integrated 3D viewing facility for existing databases containing 3D models. A preliminary version has been delivered in 2015, as a proof-of-concept, in the ADS portal (Amarna Project) and is currently under review.

The basic idea of this service is that a simple WebGL page can be automatically generated every time an item in a collection contains a 3D model. This visualization may be provided in parallel with the possibility of downloading and visualizing the model locally.

Some extensions could be implemented in other databases in a second phase, upon request by the database providers.

Figure 9: Visual Media in archaeological collections – ADS, «The Virtual Amarna Project»

The proof of concept can be viewed at:

http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/archives/view/amarna_leap_2011/

5.3.3. Landscape Services

Landscape Services were developed by CNR-ITABC and was delivered in July 2015.

This is a set of online services and tools focused on processing, management and publishing of large 3D interactive terrain datasets within collaborative workflow. Their goals within ARIADNE are (A) Aid and support 3D landscape reconstruction tasks and projects in Virtual Archaeology and (B) Provide tools for dissemination of interactive landscapes.

The service works in a similar fashion to the Visual Media Service, by providing a simple interface to the user, and is accessible to users with limited computer science and 3D modelling backgrounds.

The current version of the service is available at: <http://landscape.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/index.php>

Figure 10: ARIADNE Landscape Services – Home Page

Figure 11: ARIADNE Landscape Services – 3D terrain view

5.4. Other Services provided “as is” by partners

These existing and broadly used services will become more accessible to ARIADNE users through an index provided within the ARIADNE portal.

5.4.1. Data Deposit and Preservation Services

ADS (Archaeology Data Service) <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/archsearch/>

AIAC (Associazione Internazionale di Archeologia Classica) FASTI Online <http://www.fastionline.org/>

DAI (Deutsches Archäologisches Institute – German Archaeological Institute) online service: Arachne <http://arachne.dainst.org/> and Zenon databases <http://opac.dainst.org/>

DCCD (Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology) <http://dendro.dans.knaw.nl/>

DANS (Data Archiving and Networking Services) <http://dans.knaw.nl/> and EASY <https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/ui/browse>

6. Methodology used for evaluation

6.1. Scope of the testing

Testing is related to services implemented in the ARIADNE project and is briefly described in the previous pages.

No evaluation will be conducted for previously existing services operated by partners and made available through ARIADNE, only the newly provided access to these services through the ARIADNE Portal will be evaluated as a part of the ARIADNE portal service.

6.2. General aspects on methodology

The evaluation will be implemented in two complementary directions:

- Using predefined testing scenarios according to the following matrix
- Using open evaluation questionnaires

The evaluation cycle follows several steps:

- Preliminary tasks:
 - Creation of the group of evaluators
 - Preparation of the evaluation scheme
- Conducting the evaluation
- Analysing the results
- Producing a structured and commented feedback to the implementation team and (if necessary), and implementation of the requested changes and production of a revised version of the service/tool

6.3. Testing scenarios

Each testing scenario will be applied to one or several services for which this testing scenario is relevant, according to the following matrix:

		SERVICES								
		CATALOGUE			VISUAL MEDIA SERVICES			LANDSCAPE SERVICES		
		1.1	1.2	1.3	2.1	2.2	2.3	3.1	3.2	3.3
		Catalogue Search	Spatial Search	Timeline Search	3D Models	RTI	High Res Images	Own Cloud	3D Terrain	Terrain Gallery
ACTIONS	Navigate									
	Search									
	View									
	Edit									
	Geo Search									
	Timeline Search									
	Upload									
	Conversion									
	Manage									
	Download									
	Embed									

Notes:

- The ARIADNE Portal gives an integrated access to all the services, being designed within the ARIADNE project or not (pre-existing services). All the testing scenarios are related to this general-purpose service.
- Some use cases rely on services that are not included in the list of the services to be evaluated. It may be that these are not documented as services *per se*, or that their implementation is not scheduled. E.g. navigate and search accounts, visualize and search account attributes; prepare and register a new collection.

- Some services do not explicitly correspond to use cases. D13.1 has to be enriched to include these services. E.g. Landscape and terrain services. Landscape services are a set of responsive web services that include large terrain datasets generation, 3D landscape composing and 3D model processing.

6.3.1. Evaluation questionnaires

6.3.1.1. Content of the questionnaires

The aim of the questionnaire related to a specific service is to determine whether the service meets the expectations of the users.

Each service provider should provide, along with the service, an evaluation questionnaire giving the feedback that is most useful for the implementation team.

The useful data could be:

- The answer to precise questions about usability of the service
- Open comments about the service (usability, request for improvements, a.s.o.)
- A note given to the service (similar to what could be found in the AppStore)
- Quantitative data about usage (e.g. number of downloads of an application, number of clicks, number of files uploaded, ...)

The questionnaire prepared by the service provider must be completed by an evaluation questionnaire prepared by the teams in charge of designing the service and/or of the collection of users' needs.

A prototype of the test that will be submitted is attached in Annex II.

6.3.1.2. Translation

The questionnaires were created in English.

A partner wishing to translate them in another language may do so, to provide them to their community (*practical aspects are to be developed. In particular, this is not suitable for questionnaires submitted online directly in the web-based service*). In that case, the feedback to the task leader shall be fully translated in English, including the comments that are useful for evaluation purposes.

6.3.1.3. Operation

The questionnaire will be sent to a restricted set of users, previously identified as:

- Persons who have shown an interest for ARIADNE (respondents to the survey conducted in WP2)
- Users of the specific service willing to answer a set of questions online

The questionnaire, according to the scheme presented in Annex II, will be produced on a Google Form and will be sent to a list of testers.

The questionnaire will also be sent via the web to for those who will participate locally in the workshops for presentation of the project planned at the Inrap (Paris) during the first half of 2016.

The questionnaire will be sent a maximum of three times (monthly) to testers who don't respond. Testers who don't respond three times will be replaced in the panel.

6.3.1.4. Analysis of the data

The analysis will be made by the task leader, and in coordination with the teams D2.2 and D13.1 / D13.2.

A quarterly analysis of the data is planned. The results, transposed in appropriate graphics, will be sent to the WP leader, so it can be transmitted to other Tasks within WP13.

Particular attention will be given in the first testing to the global acceptance and implementation of the proposed services.

In the second half of 2016 the focus will be on the proper functioning of services and the speed of the operations carried out by testers.

The whole set of quarterly results will be presented into D13.5 Final Testing Report.

6.4. Other

Some partners may wish to use additional evaluation instruments. These could be useful to gain additional data from the evaluation, e.g. to have more precise comments on the usage of the services and potential improvements.

6.4.1. Individual contacts

Individual contacts can be made (phone, face-to-face or Skype meetings) either directly or after a person has answered a questionnaire and agreed to be contacted.

The contact may include a co-browsing phase by which the user navigates in the service under supervision of the evaluator. If that phase is conducted during a remote contact, the specific infrastructure has to support tracking of users actions, or the analysis could be done by using a teleconference system that allows visualization and grab the remote user's desktop.

6.4.2. Group sessions

Partners can organize a group session with several users of a service to collect information about the usage of the service. A group session allows emulation between the participants and allow more than single-contacts, but is obviously much more time-consuming.

The partner should take care of the organization and, if applicable, the specific costs of the session.

6.5. Feedback to the implementation teams

The results of the evaluation process will be sent back to the implementation team:

- Informal feedback will be sent every time important or critical feedback is received (e.g. to allow the service developers to react promptly to bug notifications)
- Formal feedback will be sent as part of the services testing report (D13.5, draft versions and final version, see hereafter the Agenda section)

6.6. Agenda

The evaluation process for any service obviously requires the full availability of the service, in a stable version upon which the implementation team has already conducted preliminary technical tests.

It also requires the availability of a comprehensive set of data appropriate to using the service.

Currently, the services that meet these criteria are the Visual Media Services, a first version of which has been delivered and upon which a first set of tests has been conducted; the Landscape Services and the Portal prototype, were delivered in November 2015.

The other services are still under implementation and may not be tested at the time of production of the first release of this report.

6.6.1. Testing of individual services

A first testing phase, which began in November 2015 and will end at the latest June 30th 2016, will consist of testing all individual services that will be delivered within the ARIADNE project.

The testing procedure is meant to last for six months from the date of availability of the service, which means all services have to be fully ready and available at the latest by the end of December 2015.

An interim testing report, summing up the results of the individual evaluation of the services, will be created and delivered by June 2016, for feedback to the service providers.

6.6.2. Overall testing

A second testing phase upon the whole system will be conducted from July to December, 2016.

This testing phase will focus on the usability of the ARIADNE service infrastructure taken as a whole, the ARIADNE portal being the entry point.

6.7. Technical infrastructure issues

Each service provider will take care of the provision of the infrastructure related to its individual service.

The task leader will ensure that no part of the infrastructure is missing or under-implemented but should not have to provide a specific technical infrastructure.

7. First evaluation results

7.1. Visual Media Services

Informal tests have been conducted by Inrap among a community of internal power users, showing a great interest in the service provided for visualization of 3D images, but also the need for enhanced visualization and analysis tools, and especially measuring tools.

This feedback meets the development plan of the Visual Media Services; the new version to be released in the first half of 2016 shall answer to this need.

8. Conclusions

Most of the work remains to be done starting in January 2016, when a comprehensive set of services will gradually be made available, including the services related to the Catalogue which are the central part of the ARIADNE project.

9. References

ARIADNE– Project Website, <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

ARIADNE, 2014, D 12.1 "User Requirements", <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D12.1-Use-Requirements>

ARIADNE, 2014, D 13.1 "Service Design", <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D13.1-Service-Design>

ARIADNE, 2015, D 2.2 "Second report on users' needs", <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/content/view/full/1188>

ARIADNE, 2015, D 12.2 "Infrastructure Design", <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D12.2-Infrastructure-Design>

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11. Annex I – Testing scenarios

11.1. Basic Catalogue Services

Scenario Group 1		Basic Catalogue Services		
Pre-requisites		Basic ICT skills User browses the ARIADNE Portal		
Step	Action	Expected result	Conclusion	Validation
1.1	Catalogue Navigate			
1.2	Catalogue Search			
1.3	Catalogue View			
1.4	Spatial Navigate			
1.5	Spatial Search			
1.6	Spatial View			
1.7	Timeline Navigate			
1.8	Timeline Search			
1.9	Timeline View			

11.2. Advanced Catalogue Services

Scenario Group 2		Advanced Catalogue Services		
Pre-requisites		Basic ICT skills Basic geo search skills Basic time search skills User browses the ARIADNE Portal User advanced search on the ARIADNE Portal		
Step	Action	Expected result	Conclusion	Validation
2.1	Catalogue Parameterise Search			
2.2	Geo Parameterise Search			
2.3	Timeline Parameterise search			

11.3. Visual Media Services

Scenario Group 3		Visual Media Services		
Pre-requisites		Advanced image processing skills User has a visual media document (3D model, RTI, HR image)		
Step	Action	Expected result	Conclusion	Validation
3.1	3D Models Navigate			
3.2	3D Models View			
3.3	3D Models Upload			
3.4	3D Models Parameter			
3.5	3D Models Transform			
3.6	3D Models Download			
3.7	3D Models Embed (on web site)			
3.8	RTI Navigate			
3.9	RTI View			
3.10	RTI Upload			
3.11	RTI Parameter			
3.12	RTI Transform			
3.13	RTI Download			
3.14	RTI Embed (on web site)			
3.15	High Res Images Navigate			
3.16	High Res Images View			
3.17	High Res Images Upload			
3.18	High Res Images Parameter			
3.19	High Res Images Transform			
3.20	High Res Images Download			
3.21	High Res Images Embed (on web site)			

11.4. Own Cloud Services

Scenario Group 4		Own Cloud Services		
Pre-requisites		Advanced ICT skills User has some geographical datasets (Raster + DEM + shp file)		
Step	Action	Expected result	Conclusion	Validation

4.1	Own Cloud Navigate			
4.2	Own Cloud (Access and) View			
4.3	Own Cloud Upload			
4.4	Own Cloud Manage			

11.5. Landscape Services

Scenario Group 5		Landscape Services		
Pre-requisites		Basic GIS skills User has uploaded a geographical dataset on Own Cloud		
Step	Action	Expected result	Conclusion	Validation
5.1	3D Terrain Navigate			
5.2	3D Terrain View			
5.3	3D Terrain Parameter			
5.4	3D Terrain Upload			
5.5	3D Terrain Transform			
5.6	Terrain Gallery Navigate			
5.7	Terrain Gallery View			
5.8	Terrain Gallery Download			
5.9	Terrain Gallery Embed (on web site)			

12. Annex II – Prototype questionnaire for the evaluation of the ARIADNE Services

TESTER DATA			
First Name			
[Text]			
Last Name			
[Text]			
Institution			
[Text]			
Country			
[Text]			
START			
How was the web site reached?			
[multiple choice]			
<i>Google</i>	<i>Direct Link</i>	<i>Ariadne Site</i>	<i>Other</i>
Was the service description provided on the web clear?			
YES		NO	
If NO, why?			
[Text]			
Was the provided service speed satisfactory?			
YES		NO	
If NO, why?			
[Text]			
Used services			

Catalog	Visual Media	Landscape								
CATALOG	VISUAL MEDIA	LANDSCAPE								
Kind of search	Which data have been uploaded?	Has the gallery been seen?								
[multiple choice]	[multiple choice]	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO						
YES	NO									
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;"><i>Text</i></td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;"><i>Geo</i></td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;"><i>Timeline</i></td> </tr> </table>	<i>Text</i>	<i>Geo</i>	<i>Timeline</i>	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">3D Models</td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">RTI Images</td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">HR Images</td> </tr> </table>	3D Models	RTI Images	HR Images	Was the models visualization satisfactory?		
<i>Text</i>	<i>Geo</i>	<i>Timeline</i>								
3D Models	RTI Images	HR Images								
How many searches have been done?	What was the total size (in Mb) of the uploaded data?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO						
YES	NO									
[multiple choice]	[Integer]	If NO, why?								
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 25%; text-align: center;">1-10</td> <td style="width: 25%; text-align: center;">10-20</td> <td style="width: 25%; text-align: center;">20-50</td> <td style="width: 25%; text-align: center;">>50</td> </tr> </table>	1-10	10-20	20-50	>50	Do you want to answer to specific questions about 3D models?	[Text]				
1-10	10-20	20-50	>50							
Was the results visualization satisfactory?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr style="background-color: #e0ffff;"> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	Have any process been run?						
YES	NO									
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	If NO, why?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO				
YES	NO									
YES	NO									
If NO, why?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr style="background-color: #90ee90;"> <td style="text-align: center;">3D MODELS</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Was the model visualization satisfactory?</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">If NO, why?</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Was the navigation speed of the model satisfactory?</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">If NO, why?</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Was the model quality satisfactory?</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">If NO, why?</td> </tr> </table>	3D MODELS	Was the model visualization satisfactory?	If NO, why?	Was the navigation speed of the model satisfactory?	If NO, why?	Was the model quality satisfactory?	If NO, why?	What kind of output has been chosen?	
3D MODELS										
Was the model visualization satisfactory?										
If NO, why?										
Was the navigation speed of the model satisfactory?										
If NO, why?										
Was the model quality satisfactory?										
If NO, why?										
[Text]	Do you want to answer to specific questions about RTI Images?	[multiple choice]								
Were the page navigation commands clear?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr style="background-color: #e0ffff;"> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 16.6%; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 16.6%; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width: 16.6%; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width: 16.6%; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 16.6%; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width: 16.6%; text-align: center;">6</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6
YES	NO									
1	2	3	4	5	6					
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	If NO, why?	What kind of resolution has been used?						
YES	NO									
If NO, why?	Was the model visualization satisfactory?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">Low</td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">Medium</td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">High</td> </tr> </table>	Low	Medium	High					
Low	Medium	High								
[Text]	If NO, why?	Has been an area defined with a shp file?								
Were links used to reach the original data?	Was the model quality satisfactory?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO						
YES	NO									
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	If NO, why?	If YES, are you satisfied?						
YES	NO									
If YES, did they work properly?	Do you want to answer to specific questions about RTI Images?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO						
YES	NO									
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr style="background-color: #e0ffff;"> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	If NO, why?				
YES	NO									
YES	NO									
Were the results satisfactory?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr style="background-color: #90ee90;"> <td style="text-align: center;">RTI IMAGES</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Was the RTI visualization satisfactory?</td> </tr> </table>	RTI IMAGES	Was the RTI visualization satisfactory?	[Text]						
RTI IMAGES										
Was the RTI visualization satisfactory?										
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO	Have files in OWN Cloud been uploaded?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr style="background-color: #e0ffff;"> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">YES</td> <td style="width: 50%; text-align: center;">NO</td> </tr> </table>	YES	NO				
YES	NO									
YES	NO									
If NO, why?	[Text]	[Text]								
[Text]	[Text]	[Text]								

YES		NO	
If YES, has an answer from the developers been received?			
YES		NO	
FINAL EVALUATION			
Have been the service performances satisfactory?			
YES		NO	
If NO, why?			
[Text]			
Have been the system used while connected to:			
[multiple choice]			
High speed network (>10MB)	Ordinary network (3-10MB)	Low speed connection (< 3MB)	
Global judgement on the experience:			
(* * * * *)			
Experience description (optional)			
[Text]			
Are any suggestions for the developers possible? (Possible suggestions for the developers:)			
YES		NO	
If YES, what?			
[Text]			
Which other data type should be managed by the Services? (Specify data type)			
[Text]			
Which visualization or interaction features should be considered while extending the Visual Media Service? (Please specify)			
[Text]			